

AFFORDing FAIR Data: An Open Research Data Index with R and Git

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This is part of AFFORD: A Framework for Avoiding the Open Research Data Dump

- We provide a simple and **affordable** workflow to facilitate making data **FAIR**
- A **data index** allows to navigate through metadata and **find** your data

Data

Findable
Accessible
Interoperable
Reusable

Metadata

code

Index

collaborators
navigate

R, Quarto and Git

R and Quarto

- A **Quarto markdown** file with R code, text and output.
- Input files: **metadata** tabular data and associated documentation
- Output: an interactive HTML table rendered with the **R** package **DT**
- In a **_quarto.yml** you can customize the webpage layout

YAML Layout settings

Markdown text

R code

Output: e.g., table

render

_quarto.yml

website

Filters

Links to data

Gitlab pages

repository

online
index

Gitlab

- Keep files in repositories with **Git version control**
- **Gitlab pages** hosts a static website
- Access can be public or private
- In Gitlab UZH your site can use SWITCH edu-ID for login

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References

R - <https://www.r-project.org/>

Quarto - <https://quarto.org/>

Gitlab - <https://about.gitlab.com/>

Gitlab UZH - <https://gitlab.uzh.ch/>

Center For Reproducible Science - <https://www.crs.uzh.ch/>

AFFORD website - https://crsuzh.pages.uzh.ch/AFFORD_website/

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